

Avionics Candidate Selection Process for ATE Test Program Development Projects

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Abstract : *This paper has been written to clearly document the specific steps utilized to ensure the selection of the proper OTPS development candidates which will, in turn, provide the optimum support for US Navy fleet aircraft at the intermediate or I level of maintenance. This process can be utilized by any organization, military or civilian, for similar selections of electronics tested on ATE that is to be replaced. The selection process is of particular interest to all parties associated with automatic test equipment (ATE) test program set (TPS) development in general and CASS TPS developers in particular. This paper will use US Navy jargon when referring to equipment and command names. Equivalent nomenclature will be provided parenthetically wherever possible if clarification is needed.*

Phase I: DATA COLLECTION/SOURCES

Listing of Potential Candidates

The initial inroads for any analysis involving the transfer of a particular electronic component from a legacy ATE to a new ATE must start with the detailed listing of the items currently under test on the legacy tester. Once the tester to be replaced is identified several sources should be queried to determine the accurate list of Units Under Test (UUTs). The Master Test Program Index (MTPSI) is supplied by the Fleet Support Team (FST) for most presently available ATE systems. Each ATE and aircraft combination will have a separate deck of MTPSI cards. These hard cards sort UUTs by part number and contain data that is key to subsequent steps in the analysis process. Key data elements are the Work Unit Code (WUC), manufacturer's part number, nomenclature, and reference designator (RefDes) for each UUT. Use of a WORD table to record this data is helpful at this point. Use of databases or spreadsheets could confuse things at this stage. See Figure 1 for a typical table.

NIIN translation via AV-3M

National Item Identification Numbers (NIINs) must be obtained for each UUT. This number is the key to unlocking the cost and usage data kept and tracked by the supply system. Part number to NIIN translation is accomplished via use of one of commercially available products such as HAYSTACK or by use of AV-3M report number A7707-01, 02, 04 available via internet at <https://www.nalda.navy.mil/av3mapps/av-3m/av3mrpt.cfm>. This is a password protected site

with access available via on-line form for requesting userid/password. NIIN should be added to table of data.

Other data sources such as the AV-8B and S-3B Consolidated Avionics Master Equipment List (CAMEL), F/A-18 Avionics Interchangeability Matrix (AIM), and direct input from FST representatives should provide these data elements at the very minimum. Additional data sources include interviews with Fleet repair site representatives, avionics system manufacturers, and Type Commander (TYCOM) representatives.

Cost Data - NAVICP or Other Central Supply Point

In order for any proper analysis of the need for testability at the intermediate level of maintenance a valid source of cost data must be identified. The Naval Inventory Control Point (NAVICP) is our preferred source of this information. NAVICP's database of cost and related information is known as SNAPSHOT. Access to this data is available via the internet at <https://nast20.nalda.navy.mil/>. This site is password protected using the same userid/password established in previous paragraph. After accessing site select the "supply analysis" tool then select the "NAVICP NSN Snapshot" tool. Using the national Stock Number (NSN) for the avionics to be analyzed, the following data should be obtained:

1. Cost using the "STD PRICE" field
2. AVDLR using "RPT NET PRICE"
3. Record the quality On Hand in both Ready For Issue (RFI) and Not Ready For Issue (NRFI) rows
4. Record the quality Due In both RFI and NRFI

5. Record the Quarterly Demand for this item. See Figure 2 for the location of each of these items on the web page.

UUT Reliability Data

Fleet avionics usage data is available from the Naval Aviation Maintenance Office (NAMO). The data is reported by Fleet maintenance sites and stored by NAMO in a database that is accessed by registered users via dial-up or internet connections. One of the data reporting systems within the NAMO data collection system is Equipment Condition Analysis (ECA). ECA is a collection of prestructured reports for various applications that utilize the Fleet reported maintenance data as its basis.

ECA report used for our analysis is the IMA Summary, R0572A, which provides details of maintenance activity for a particular WUC over a selected time span within a specific aircraft community. Data reported includes total maintenance actions (EMT Actions), total maintenance time (EMT Time), flight hours for aircraft type during time span selected, and detailed maintenance activity sorted by malfunction (MAL) codes in a time-based matrix format. The R0572A concludes with a comprehensive report of all part numbers reported against the selected WUC. See Figure 3 for an example of this report. As a backup to this report we also have the R0573A report that provides the same data but is based on a selected part number and ends with reported WUCs (the reverse of the R0572A).

A calculated Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) is the data element to be extracted from the ECA report. To get this total the number of maintenance actions with MAL codes of 799 (no defect), all 800 series (removed to facilitate other maintenance). Subtract this from the total EMT actions to get a number of maintenance actions that reflect actual field failures. Divide the Total Flight Hours by the modified total failures to get a Mean Flight Hours Between Maintenance Actions which we use as the MTBF. As before, enter this in the Word table in the MTBF column.

Data is now in a form that can be utilized for analysis using Level Of Repair Analysis (LORA) version 88-007 or any other analysis tool/method.

Data Manipulation and Analysis

Data transcribed from MTPSI or other sources will be in a fairly random sequence and must be put in proper order. Using the table produced with all of the data elements included, sort on WUC (ascending) then on part number (descending). Sorting items in this manner will group the whole systems together with UUT candidates sorted so that they are in WUC sequence which, in turn, puts parent Weapons Replaceable Assemblies (WRAs) just above their Shop Replaceable Assembly (SRA) children. The SRAs will be in order of RefDes (A1, A2,...) as they are listed in Fleet technical manuals. Sorting the part numbers in descending order generally puts the highest revision level at the top of the list. This is normally the latest "dash" number that is in use by Fleet units.

Use of sorting routines in Access or Excel tends to confuse the WUC/part number sort since both numbers are alphanumeric and sort differently in Word. Past experience has revealed that the WUC manuals in the Fleet are currently in the same sequence as a normal Word sort. In addition, use of Excel can cause some WUCs to be automatically translated incorrectly. EX: 743E100 becomes 7.43E+1 which must be spotted and manually repaired after reformatting the WUC column, a task not easily accomplished with a thousand rows of data or more.

PHASE II: USE OF LORA SOFTWARE AS AN ANALYSIS TOOL

LORA 88-007

Level of Repair Analysis (LORA) model 88-007 was created by Naval Air Systems Command, Maintenance Policy and Planning Division (AIR-411) as a means to consistently determine the proper level to repair items under their cognizance for the optimum support of deployed units. Our use of their tool is as a statistically accurate means to sort the universe of potential offload candidate UUTs into three areas: UUTs that require I level support and those UUTs that do not. Further analysis of LORA output could be utilized as a preliminary source of a repair level for those UUTs that are not listed as needing to be I level repairable. Note that the non-candidate recommendations of "depot repair" or "consumable" is merely an indication that further analysis is needed given that no I level repair will be done.

Input data used in the LORA model was based on the latest default data guide to establish common data entries for items such as supply system item entry cost and cost per square foot of storage onboard a typical aircraft carrier. Using these common data elements allows us to keep all variables in the decision process constant except unit cost and MTBF, our two variables. Each aircraft under evaluation has a tailored model setup to account for a typical year of flight hour data at the appropriate site types. See Figure 4 for typical input data screens and the data elements used.

Running this software is an easy task once the operator gets reaccustomed to using DOS rather than Windows operating system. Use of some of the newer LORA tools has been proven to hinder the sorting process rather than enhancing it. The new tools are overly complex for our needs thus excessive time is needed to achieve the same results. The basic process entails entering the program once for each WUC, entering the WUC in the top row, then placing the cost and calculated MTBF in the appropriate places. The tool will process the data briefly and the output can then be saved in a text file. This file will be appended each time the tool is run and is Word editable.

A typical page of an output file of the LORA program is attached in Figure 5. The "Least Cost Alternative" amount is compared to the three items (excluding the crossed out selections which are not options in this analysis). The outcome of I level, Consumable or Depot can easily be seen. The numerical amount, which relates to total life cycle cost, is irrelevant. Only the decision to which they point is of interest.

Record each LORA decision in the "Candidate" column in the Word table as "Yes" (which represents an I level repair decision), "No, Consumable" or "No, Depot". Data is now in a form that can be reviewed and analyzed.

Phase III: FORMAL REVIEW/APPROVAL

FST Review

The Fleet Support Team for each aircraft will receive the Word file that has been sorted into Candidate and Non-Candidate lists for ease of review. Analysis of this data will be accomplished in two stages.

First, the list of proposed candidates is reviewed to determine if there are whole WUC groupings that

can be deleted due to parent system obsolescence or pending removal via scheduled and approved/funded avionics changes (AVCs). These AVCs must be funded in order to ensure that future decision changes will not adversely effect the candidate list. Proposed AVCs should be entertained but final modifications to the list should be withheld until final AVC status is firm.

Further analysis of the candidate list will delete all individual part numbers that are obsolete or will be obsolete by the time the proposed Test Programs are to be delivered for use at I level. Deleting these excess "dash numbers" will allow for more efficient data collection efforts and will provide the optimum support for each dollar expended.

Second, the list of proposed non-candidates is reviewed to determine if there are any items that should be moved onto the Candidate list. Movement onto the Candidate list must be supported by a clearly defined reason that is defensible and repeatable based on hard metrics. Typically items move up due to an actual higher level if use in the field than is readily seen during a cursory analysis of NALDA data. Large numbers of SRAs have "hidden" use data due to maintenance that is charged to the next higher assembly, the parent WRA. Other reasons for the shift onto the Candidate list include an anticipated increase in avionics use that would cause a corresponding increase in demand, a requirement for I level repair of flight critical components regardless of analytical analysis output, high levels of increased AVDLR cost beyond the available limits of current funding by aircraft program offices when present failure rate is seen from depot's increased workload point of view.

Changes to these lists are entered in the appropriate places. The lists are resorted. Summary data is determined and entered at the top of each list (Box score) for ease of use by all concerned. The data is now ready for final review/approval.

Aircraft Program Office Review/Approval

The Candidate and Non-Candidate lists are presented to the Aircraft Program Office for the appropriate airframe. Normally the review by the FST is accepted. Minor adjustments can be made, if needed, due to new changes in AVC status or other issues. Formal approval is transmitted via letter to the Test Program Set acquisition lists team with the Candidate and Non-Candidate lists included as attachments.

At this point the Candidate list is ready for inclusion in a Commerce Business Daily solicitation, or equivalent Request for Proposal.

establishment/refinement of related test program set development processes.

The Non-Candidate list forwarded to the FST for further action. Decisions should be made to mitigate the impact in manpower and funding of the eventual loss of I level test/repair capability for each items listed. Source, Maintainability, and Recoverability (SM&R) codes must be formally changed as will their corresponding entries in the avionics manuals in use in the field. Depots must be prepared for the increase in workload even though this process has pushed the high use items to I level and "weeded out" the items that are, or will soon be, deleted from active use.

FUTURE IMPACT

Use by Other Services or Agencies

This process, summarized in Process Flowchart.doc, can be easily modified for use by other military services or any comparable civilian agency that uses multi-level maintenance to support a wide range of electronics systems, boxes, circuit cards, and sub-assemblies. Key elements that must be available are adequate field repair data, current cost data, and an accurate estimate for the proposed new test setup to be considered.

CONCLUSIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

This process has been refined over ten years to reflect changes in the review/approval process which have been impacted by the manner in which the division of work has been changed from centralized to field office based program office representatives. Overall the process should continue to be utilized as the most efficient manner to separate the UUTs that actually require I level support from the universe of items that have previously been placed at I level over time.

Recommendations

It is recommended that this process be subjected to a peer review so that others in fields that are relevant can provide positive suggestions for enhancement to make this process more global in it's ability for use. Once this has been accomplished it can be used as a benchmark for

<ATE> Offload to CASS

<A/C> Candidate List

With 3M and ASO Data

Current as of 14 Jan 99

<A/C> Box Score:

Post APML Review:	WRAs= 0	SRAs= 1
Post FST Review:	WRAs= 0	SRAs= 1
Post LORA:	WRAs= 0	SRAs= 2
Pre LORA:	WRAs= 0	SRAs= 4

0 WRA/4 SRA

WUC	MPNO	NOUNNOM	NSN	COST	AVDLR	MTBF	OH	DI	QD	Candidate
761H2A0	6952654-1	Control Store Page	01-263-1471	9670	4240	4932	22/0	2/1	8.23	Yes
739F6G0	130725-2	Manchester Interface	00-123-0168	4289	2300	16248	0	4/2	2.14	No Depot
73X3D31	5812426G1	Refresh Mem Strg	01-256-7876	11580	4910	64224	4/3	6/1	0.50	No Consumable
73X3D32	5812418G1	Refresh Mem Cntr	01-256-7877	3980	1390	8250	0/9	0	0	Dropped - APML

Figure 1: Sample Of Word Table Used To Store Data During Analysis Process

File Edit View Go Window Help

Bookmarks Netsite: https://nast20.nalda.navy.mil/cgi-bin/ssm_tier2_snap_build.pl What's Related

NSN Snapshot Summary

5/19/99
NIIN: 013932647

NSN: 7R H 1290 013932647 CS **LRC:** HZA **PLT:** 5.1
NAME: PANEL, CONTROL, ELECT

DRIPR: -X- -M- **ROL:** 26 **WEAR OUT:** .11 **FGC:** 3U7A
RTC: L1ZHVDX **EOQ:** 2 **SURVIVAL:** .89 **HEAD/MEM:** H
SOURCE: P **ISC:** 5 3H C **ENTRY DATE:** 1994-07-09 **LVL AUTH:** 22
SHELF: 0 **U/I:** EA **HOLD DATE:** **PAC:** KE
IMEC: **GAINING IM COG:** **IMC:** E
QUARTERLY DEMAND: 13.18

STOCK STATUS	ON HAND	DUE IN	DUE OUT	TOTAL PR
RFI:	15	16	15	0
NON-RFI:	103	0	0	0
PUR-ALL:	12	1	0	0

BACKORDERS: 11 **STD PRICE:** \$40110 **ITEM RPR COST:** \$15108.23
DUE-IN: 16 **REPL PRICE:** \$25360 **RPT NET PRICE:** \$26220

Document Done

Start Sent Items - Microsoft Out... Microsoft Word - THE Pap... NSN Snapshot Summ... 9:42 AM

Figure 2: Sample Of SNAPSHOT Data From WEB

REPORT NBR: R572A
 PREPARED: 17 NOV 1994

EQUIPMENT CONDITION ANALYSIS

REPORT PERIOD: 1 JAN 93 THRU 31 DEC 93

IMA SUMMARY

T/M: F18
 WUC: 4431421 * CONVERTER CIRCUIT CARD ASSEMBLY
 ORG: GF1 P9F GG1 GN1 WN7 FEL A9G C94
 TOTAL EMT ACTIONS: 94
 TOTAL EMT TIME: 765.9
 TOTAL VERIFIED FAILURES: 0
 TOTAL FLIGHT HOURS: 239,801.5
 MEAN FLTRHS BETWEEN FAILURES: *

INT HRS	IMA MALFUNCTION CODES										TOT ACTNS BY INT	% OF TOT ACTNS	EMT BY INT	% OF TOT EMT
	070	127	160	255	290	374	615	703	900	900				
1	1	1	2		1	3				1	9	9.6	6.1	.8
2	5		6	2	9					1	23	24.5	39.8	5.2
3		1	3	3	3						10	10.6	26.3	3.4
4	3				1						4	4.3	14.5	1.9
5		1	1	2							4	4.3	20.0	2.6
6	2			1							3	3.2	17.0	2.2
7	2			2							5	5.3	33.7	4.4
8	1			2			1				4	4.3	31.3	4.1
9	2			2							4	4.3	33.8	4.4
10				2							2	2.1	19.8	2.6
11				4							4	4.3	43.2	5.6
12				3							4	4.3	47.1	6.1
16				4		2					6	6.4	82.4	10.8
20				1							1	1.1	17.8	2.3
24				3							3	3.2	67.0	8.7
>24				7							7	7.4	217.0	28.3
>48				1							1	1.1	49.1	6.4

TOTAL EMT ACTIONS :
 % OF TOTAL ACTIONS :
 TOTAL EMT BY MAL CODE :
 % OF TOTAL EMT :

REPORTED PART NUMBERS: 6120315 :6120313
 Maint Actions = Total EMT Actions (94) - 799 "No Defects" (0) = 94
 MTBF = Total Flight Hours/Maint Actions 239802/94 = 2551 hours

Figure 3: Sample of R0572A Report from NALDA system

RUN SPECIFICATIONS

[MAX] [MAX]
 [100] 1 = NUMBER OF ITEMS [50] 1 = NUMBER OF GSE TYPES [50] 0 = NUMBER OF SPACE TYPES
 [30] 4 = NUMBER OF SITES [50] 3 = NUMBER OF PERSONNEL TYPES [10] 8 = NUMBER OF MAINT. ALTERNATIVES
 [10] 1 = NUMBER OF AIRCRAFT TYPES [50] 0 = NUMBER OF DOCUMENTATION TYPES [5] 1 = NUMBER OF SENSITIVITY GROUPS

SYSTEM DATA

20 = LIFE CYCLE (YEARS) 17.30 = FIELD SUPPLY ADM. COST (\$/SITE-ITEM-YR) 1.00 = DEGRADATION FACTOR
 10.00 = DISCOUNT RATE (PCT) 491 = ITEM ENTRY COST (\$/ITEM) 1 = EQUIPMENT/AIRCRAFT
 52.00 = PROCUREMENT LEADTIME (WEEKS) 288 = ITEM RETENTION COST (\$ ITEM-YR) 0.00 = PERCENT DEP BACKUP
 12.00 = SAFETY LEVEL (WEEKS) 42.90 = PACKING COST FACTOR (\$/CU.FT.)

(Default data)

REPAIR CYCLE TIMES (DAYS)

	CV-PIMA	CV-DEPOT	LB-PIMA	LB-DEPOT	CV-PIMA-DEP	LB-PIMA-DEP	CV-CV	LB-LB	PIMA-PIMA
WRA	18.00	119.00	18.00	119.00	137.00	137.00	5.50	11.00	11.00
SRA, SUB-SRA	18.00	119.00	18.00	119.00	137.00	137.00	5.50	11.00	11.00

(Default data)

REQUIRED DAYS STOCK (DAYS)

	GSE SPACE COST (\$/SQ.FT.)	INVENTORY STORAGE COST (\$/CU.FT.)	HOURLY RATES (\$/HR)
90.00 = CV DISCARD	126.00 = CV	102.00 = CV	13.03 = MILITARY - CV
30.00 = LB DISCARD	2.10 = LB	2.10 = LB	28.50 = MILITARY - LB
	2.10 = PIMA	2.10 = DEPOT	30.56 = CIVILIAN
	2.10 = DEPOT		

(Default data)

INPUT DATA - SITE

SITE NO.	NAME	TYPE	# OF SITES	DAYS STOCK	PIMA PCT	AIRCRAFT DATA		FLYING DEPLOY		DISTANT REPAIR DATA		SUPPLY SHIPPING COST
						#	HOURS	FACTOR	TRANSPORT COST	ID	PCT	
1	CV	1	12	90.0	0.0	F18	20	60.0	0.400 (40%)	4	100	4.18
2	NAS-FLEET	2	2	30.0	0.0	F18	240	30.0	0.600 (60%)	4	100	2.38
3	NAS-RAG	2	2	30.0	0.0	F18	84	33.0	1.000 (100%)	4	100	2.38
4	DEPOT	4	1	0.0	0.0							0.00

In this case (the F-18):

Sites x # of A/C x Flying Hrs/month x Deploy Factor x 12 months/yr = Total flight hrs/Site Name

Site	Total Flight Hrs
CV	69,120
NAS-FLEET (A/C that are available at sea 40% and ashore 60%)	103,680
NAS-RAG (A/C that are available ashore 100%)	66,528
DEPOT	0
TOTAL	239,320

This compares favorably to the 239,801.5 flight hours reported via the R0572A for CY 1993 for the F-18 series airframe.

F-18 SRA LORA MODEL
01/26/96 09:50:40

NAVAL AIR SYSTEMS COMMAND
LEVEL OF REPAIR ANALYSIS - MOD 3 RELEASE 3C (SN 88-007)

PAGE: 3

ITEM	MFG PART NO.	NOMENCLATURE	EQUIPMENT BREAKDOWN				UNIT COST
			PREDICTED MTBF	EXPECTED MTBF	EXPECTED MTBF		
WRA 100	123ABC	ANY F-18 SRA	2551	5000	4902	15000	

(NALDA R-572A and NAVICP data)

INPUT DATA - ITEM

ITEM	QUANTITY	WEIGHT	VOLUME	PARTS	FLT-HR	PIECE OF HRS/	FALSE REMOVALS	TOTAL NET	IMA	PIMA	IMA	PIMA	DEPOT	MATERIAL RATE	IMA	PIMA	DEPOT	SCRAP RATE
WRA 100	1	3.00	1.00000	1	1.00	1.00	0.02	0.90	0.05	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

(Estimated data)

NAVAL AIR SYSTEMS COMMAND
 LEVEL OF REPAIR ANALYSIS - MOD 3 RELEASE 3C (SN 88-007)

INPUT DATA - GSE AND TRAINING HARDWARE

NAME	BACKUP	AUTH	COST	SQ FT	SUPPORT COST -- INITIAL SUBSEQUENT	DEVELOPMENT COST	TRAINING HARDWARE I-LEVEL	D-LEVEL
WRA TPS	1		-14472	0.30	0.090 0.013	266200	0	0

INPUT DATA - MANPOWER

NAME	AUTH	COST	ATTRITION RATE	BACKUP
C	24	0	0.381	
L	4	0	0.381	
DP	2	0	0.090	

(Default data)

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS SPECIFICATIONS

NO. OF GRP STEPS DATA ELEMENT	A	LOW VALUE	HIGH VALUE	SITE CLASS	INDENT LEVEL	TASK RES. TYPE TASK	SPECIFIC SITES OR ITEMS	SPECIFIC A/C TYPE
1	M	0.00	1.00	C L P D	W S X	V R D S		
7.	M	0.00	1.00		X X X			

NON-REOPTIMIZED ALTERNATIVES: ALL STANDARD ONES

REOPTIMIZED ALTERNATIVES: ALL STANDARD ONES

Figure 4: Sample LORA Input Data Elements With Data Source Identified

Typical LORA Total LCC output

NAVAL AIR SYSTEMS COMMAND
LEVEL OF REPAIR ANALYSIS - MOD 3 RELEASE 3C (SN 88-007)

TOTAL LIFE CYCLE LOGISTICS COST
(ALL COSTS ARE IN \$000)

(Consumable)	
ALL WRA'S DISCARD	
935066.7	
0.0	
0.0	
935066.7	

(I level)	
ALL WRA'S LOCAL	
17260.7	
0.0	
0.0	
17260.7	

(Depot level)	
ALL WRA'S DEPOT	
61122.8	
0.0	
0.0	
61122.8	

LEAST COST ALTERNATIVE	
17260.7	
0.0	
0.0	
17260.7	

WRA LEVEL
SRA LEVEL
SUB-SRA LEVEL
TOTAL

WRA LEVEL
SRA LEVEL
SUB-SRA LEVEL
TOTAL

WRA LEVEL
SRA LEVEL
SUB-SRA LEVEL
TOTAL

Note: "X"ed out areas represent portions of the LORA model that we do not use. In this case the Least Cost Alternative suggest repair at I level.

Figure 5: Sample LORA Outout Data